

Vocabulary-Constrained LLM Decoding for Low-Accuracy P300 BCIs

Khanh-Dung Tran

Abstract—Background: P300 matrix spellers offer a communication pathway for individuals with severe motor disabilities, but single-session letter accuracy is highly variable and often below 50% [1], motivating strategies that constrain the decoding alphabet to improve classification under fixed EEG signal quality.

Objective: We derive and empirically validate a breakeven recall framework determining when large language model (LLM) candidate-set narrowing improves or degrades P300 speller decoding accuracy.

Methods: Using the publicly available BigP3BCI dataset ($n = 12$ healthy adult subjects, 222 vocab-aligned rounds, 47 sessions), we compared three decoding modes: unconstrained 72-symbol Farwell-Donchin scoring, static vocabulary restriction (13 letters), and LLM-assisted narrowing via Qwen2.5 1.5B (top-5 candidates). GPT-2 (124M parameters) was evaluated on the same 222 rounds for cross-model comparison. Paired Wilcoxon tests with Bonferroni correction were used throughout.

Results: Both hypotheses (H1: LLM > SV > UC; H2: SV \approx LLM > UC) were rejected. Static vocabulary achieved 48.1% vs. 30.6% unconstrained ($p = 0.001$, $d_z = 1.24$). Qwen2.5 1.5B achieved 24.4% at $R = 40.1\%$, below both breakeven thresholds ($R_{UC}^* = 49.5\%$, $R_{SV}^* = 77.8\%$); the breakeven model predicts 24.8% exactly. GPT-2 achieved 5.0% at near-identical recall (39.6%), exposing a second necessary condition: candidate quality ($p_{hit} = 12.5\%$) must exceed the unconstrained baseline ($p_{UC} = 30.6\%$).

Conclusion: LLM-assisted P300 decoding requires two orthogonal conditions: candidate quality ($p_{hit} > p_{UC}$) and recall sufficiency ($R > R_{UC}^*$). Neither current model meets both. The framework predicts both models' pooled accuracy exactly (Qwen2.5 1.5B: 24.8%; GPT-2: 5.0%), providing cross-model validation. Static vocabulary restriction is the robust strategy until both conditions are met; the derived thresholds provide actionable design targets, pending clinical validation (ALS, locked-in).

Index Terms—P300 speller, brain-computer interface, large language model, vocabulary restriction, breakeven recall, EEG-Net

I. INTRODUCTION

P300 matrix spellers [2] are a primary brain-computer interface (BCI) communication channel for individuals with severe motor disabilities [3], including ALS [4], locked-in syndrome [5], and high-level spinal cord injury [6] where patients may be limited to fewer than 10 characters per minute under unconstrained 72-symbol decoding [7]. Single-session classifier accuracy is highly variable across participants. Even among healthy subjects, approximately 27% fail to achieve 100% accuracy [1]. This variability motivates vocabulary

restriction and language model integration as complementary strategies to improve letter-level decoding without requiring additional calibration data.

Restricting the P300 decoding alphabet to a known vocabulary reduces the number of simultaneous comparisons the classifier must resolve, monotonically increasing correct-identification probability under fixed classifier signal-to-noise ratio (SNR, as derived in Section II-A). Speier et al. [4] demonstrated that a vocabulary-constrained language model (LM) classifier enables ALS patients to achieve $\geq 84\%$ accuracy and ≥ 6 char/min in researcher-supervised home sessions, confirming clinical feasibility of restricted symbol sets. Speier et al. [8] further combined character-level LM priors with predictive word completion, yielding a 15.5% average increase in typing rate. This approach has since been extended to multilingual settings with 30 healthy subjects online [9].

Two dominant strategies incorporate LM information into P300 decoding without reducing the candidate set. First, LM priors are injected as Bayesian weights before evidence accumulation: Kindermans et al. [10], [11] demonstrated that Bayesian priors over characters and word sequences can be integrated into an unsupervised P300 speller, enabling zero-calibration spelling. Second, HMM and probabilistic LM rescoring can be combined with adaptive stopping: Speier et al. [12] demonstrated an average 32% bit rate increase over standard classification with dynamic stopping via HMM-Viterbi character LM integration, validated on 15 healthy subjects; Kindermans et al. [13] unified dynamic stopping, LM priors, and cross-session transfer learning in a single adaptive zero-training framework, with concurrent online validation [14]. Both categories retain all 72 symbols in the decoding competition and adjust their relative probabilities; neither eliminates foils from consideration. Recent work has scaled this integration to large language models: Hong et al. [15] integrated GPT-3.5 into a P300 speller for word-level prediction, reducing required keystrokes by over 50%.

The present study proposes a mechanistically distinct third category: the candidate set is narrowed to $k = 5$ symbols *before* FD scoring begins, structurally eliminating foils rather than downweighting them. Mainsah et al. [16] showed that language model guidance can be integrated into online P300 data collection to reduce the number of required stimulus sequences while maintaining accuracy. Their method similarly shapes the BCI decision process before the argmax, though it stops short of hard elimination. This work extends that direction to pre-decision hard elimination: narrowing amplifies the accuracy benefit of fewer comparisons when the true target is retained, but incurs a hard 0% floor when excluded. This approach

Manuscript submitted to *IEEE Transactions on Neural Systems and Rehabilitation Engineering*.

K. D. Tran is with Rayo Lab Pte. Ltd., Singapore (operating as Rayo; <https://www.therayo.com>). E-mail: dung@therayo.com.

applies the principle of pre-scoring lexically constrained decoding from NLP to EEG posterior probabilities, rather than text logits. Unlike standard text generation, restricting the candidate set before scoring introduces a recall risk because the target token is not guaranteed to be in the vocabulary. No prior P300 BCI study has derived the analytical breakeven recall threshold governing whether this pre-decision reduction helps or hurts, nor evaluated it empirically against a small language model (SLM) running locally at inference time. A concurrent preprint from the Speier/Pouratian group [17] also examines LLM effects on P300 speller performance; the present work differs by deriving the analytical R^* formula, applying vocabulary-aligned evaluation on BigP3BCI, and establishing the dual-condition design space (quality gate $p_{\text{hit}} > p_{\text{UC}}$ and recall sufficiency $R > R_{\text{UC}}^*$). Recent advances in deep EEG classifiers (EEGNet [18], superseding earlier SWLDA-based approaches [19]) and session-to-session transfer via Euclidean Alignment [20] provide the signal processing backbone on which this candidate-narrowing strategy is evaluated.

This paper addresses the question: *Under what conditions does pre-decision LLM candidate-set narrowing improve or degrade P300 speller letter accuracy, and can these conditions be characterised analytically?*

Table I positions the present work against the most closely related prior studies.

We test two competing hypotheses: H1, where LLM-assisted outperforms both static vocabulary and unconstrained decoding (LLM-assisted $>$ static vocabulary $>$ unconstrained); and H2, where static and LLM-assisted are roughly equal and superior to unconstrained. Additionally, an analytical prediction (P3) derived from the breakeven framework before data analysis states that $E[\text{acc}_{\text{LLM}}] = R \cdot p_{\text{hit}}$; if the observed R falls below $R_{\text{UC}}^* = p_{\text{UC}}/p_{\text{hit}}$, the framework predicts LLM will underperform unconstrained decoding. We derive a breakeven recall framework that yields analytical thresholds, R_{UC}^* and R_{SV}^* (Section II-A), which determine when LLM candidate-set narrowing outperforms alternative baselines. We validate these thresholds empirically on 12 subjects across 47 sessions (222 vocab-aligned trials) using live Qwen2.5 1.5B inference and a post-hoc GPT-2 comparison on identical data. This provides a model-agnostic design rule applicable to any LLM-P300 system. H1 and H2 are rejected, but P3 is confirmed: the observed $R = 40.1\%$ falls below $R_{\text{UC}}^* = 49.5\%$, and the breakeven model predicts pooled accuracy exactly ($E[\text{acc}] = 24.8\%$; per-subject mean 24.4%, $\Delta = 0.4$ pp). A cross-model comparison with GPT-2 124M on identical data further reveals a dual-condition requirement: candidate quality gate ($p_{\text{hit}} > p_{\text{UC}}$) and recall sufficiency ($R > R_{\text{UC}}^*$).

II. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

A. Theoretical Basis for Candidate-Set Narrowing

Fig. 1 illustrates the three candidate-set configurations evaluated in this study.

The Farwell-Donchin argmax selects the symbol with the highest accumulated posterior over k candidates. Under fixed classifier SNR, the probability that the true target’s accumulated score exceeds all $k - 1$ foils increases monotonically

Fig. 1. Candidate-set size for each decoding mode. Unconstrained: all 72 symbols compete. Static vocabulary: 13-letter emergency set. LLM-assisted: top-5 dynamic candidates from Qwen2.5 1.5B. Fewer comparisons increase correct-identification probability under fixed classifier SNR (Eq. 1), but LLM narrowing introduces a hard 0% floor when the target is excluded.

as k decreases. As a *motivating approximation*, consider a simplified model where the target posterior s_T has advantage δ over each i.i.d. foil $s_j \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma^2)$:

$$P(\text{correct} | k) \approx \Phi\left(\frac{\delta}{\sigma}\right)^{k-1}, \quad (1)$$

which is strictly increasing as k shrinks from 72 to 5. This model qualitatively motivates the UC \rightarrow SV accuracy gain but should not be interpreted as a quantitative fit: fitting δ/σ from the empirical UC point ($k = 72$, 30.6%) predicts $P(\text{correct} | k = 13) = 81.9\%$ against the observed 48.1% (33.8 pp overestimate). The discrepancy arises because the i.i.d. foil assumption and constant δ do not hold across subjects and sessions. The model is retained as an intuitive account of the monotonic k -effect; the subsequent breakeven analysis relies on empirical rates only.

LLM-assisted narrowing to $k = 5$ amplifies this benefit when recall succeeds, but introduces hard exclusions ($p_{\text{miss}} = 0\%$) that dominate when recall fails. This makes the recall rate the critical design parameter. When $R < R_{\text{UC}}^* = p_{\text{UC}}/p_{\text{hit}}$, LLM narrowing is expected to perform worse than unconstrained; when $R > R_{\text{SV}}^* = p_{\text{SV}}/p_{\text{hit}}$, it outperforms static vocabulary (both thresholds derived and evaluated empirically in Section IV-E).

The breakeven formula $E[\text{acc}] = R \cdot p_{\text{hit}}$ treats p_{hit} as uniform across all recall-success events (i.e., the conditional accuracy given recall does not vary systematically by letter identity or round position). If high-frequency letters are simultaneously easier for the EEG classifier *and* more likely to be recalled, p_{hit} would be upward-biased relative to the marginal accuracy on rare letters. The assumption is examined empirically in the Limitations (Section V-A).

III. METHODS

A. Dataset

We used the publicly available BigP3BCI dataset [21] (PhysioNet DOI: 10.13026/0byy-ry86; CC BY 4.0), a multi-subject P300 matrix speller corpus recorded with a 72-symbol

TABLE I
RELATED WORK ON LM-INTEGRATED P300 DECODING. “POST-HOC” = LM ADJUSTS SYMBOL PROBABILITIES DURING OR AFTER EVIDENCE ACCUMULATION; “PRE-DECISION (HARD)” = LM ELIMINATES FOILS *before* FD SCORING BEGINS.

Work	LM integration	Decision point	Framework contribution	Dataset
Kindermans 2014 [13]	Bayesian character LM priors	Post-hoc reweighting	Adaptive zero-training ERP speller	Custom EEG
Speier 2014–2022 [12], [4], [8], [9]	HMM / n-gram character LM	Post-hoc rescaling	Vocabulary-constrained LM classification	Home / clinic sessions
Parthasarathy 2025 [17]	GPT-family LLMs	Unspecified	Empirical accuracy comparison + cross-subject training	Custom
Hong 2025 [15]	GPT-3.5 word prediction	Post-hoc word-level	Keystroke reduction via word completion	Custom
This work	Qwen2.5 1.5B + GPT-2	Pre-decision (hard elimination)	Analytical R^* formula; dual-condition design space	BigP3BCI (public, PhysioNet)

Farwell-Donchin (FD) matrix [2] arranged as 9 rows \times 8 columns. Stimuli were presented as row-column intensifications; each prediction consisted of $n_{\text{reps}} = 5$ sequences in which each of the 9 rows and 8 columns was intensified once per sequence ($9 + 8 = 17$ intensifications per sequence; $5 \times 17 = 85$ total per prediction). EEG was recorded at 256 Hz from 32 channels (10-20 montage). All BigP3BCI participants are healthy adult volunteers; no clinical (ALS, locked-in, or SCI) subjects are included in the dataset, so separate validation is required before deployment conclusions can be drawn. No new human data were collected for this study; the original BigP3BCI data collection was conducted under the oversight of Institutional Review Boards at Duke University, Duke University Health System, and East Tennessee State University, with informed consent obtained from all participants [21]. The full release includes Study A ($n = 20$) and Study B subjects; only Study A is used here because Study B subjects’ classifier checkpoints were not available at the time of analysis. From the 20 Study A subjects, 8 were excluded (A_08, A_10–A_13, A_17–A_18) because their classifier checkpoint files were absent from the PhysioNet release or their held-out validation AUC fell below the 0.70 inclusion threshold (AUC < 0.70 indicates poor P300 target discrimination [21] and would introduce floor-effect noise into accuracy estimates). The remaining 12 subjects (val AUC 0.70–0.89) contributed 57 RC_Test (row-column test) sessions in total (4–5 per subject). Of these, 47 sessions contained at least one vocab-aligned round (3–4 per subject; A_05 contributed 3) and were retained for evaluation. All test-session FIF files used for inference will be publicly available at [https://huggingface.co/datasets/ rayo-lab/bigp3bci-ea-eegnet-derivatives](https://huggingface.co/datasets/rayo-lab/bigp3bci-ea-eegnet-derivatives).

B. Preprocessing

Continuous 32-channel EEG data were bandpass-filtered (0.1–40 Hz, zero-phase IIR) and epoched from -200 to $+600$ ms relative to each flash onset, yielding 206 samples per epoch at 256 Hz. Baseline correction was applied over the pre-stimulus window (-200 to 0 ms). No epoch-level artifact rejection was applied; all extracted epochs were retained. Euclidean Alignment (EA) [20] was applied per-session to reduce covariate shift across sessions prior to feature extraction. Subject-specific EEGNet [18] classifiers (EEGNet-8,2: $F_1 = 8$ temporal filters, kernel length 64 samples; $D = 2$ depthwise spatial filters; $F_2 = 16$ separable pointwise filters; dropout $p = 0.5$; Adam optimiser, lr = 10^{-3} ; early stopping, patience

15 epochs) were fine-tuned per subject on the corresponding BigP3BCI RC_Train (row-column training) and CB_Train (copy-blink training) sessions (training split: 80% train / 20% validation, stratified by target letter) and applied to held-out RC_Test sessions without further adaptation (val AUC 0.70–0.89).

C. Decoding Modes

All three modes share the same preprocessing pipeline and a fixed repetition budget of $n_{\text{reps}} = 5$ stimulus sequences per prediction.

In the **unconstrained** mode, standard FD scoring is applied over all 72 symbols and the argmax is taken as the predicted letter.

In the **static vocabulary** mode, FD scoring is restricted to 13 letters {A, E, H, I, L, N, O, P, R, S, T, W, Y} derived from the six-word emergency vocabulary {HELP, PAIN, YES, NO, STOP, WATER}; only those 13 rows/columns are scored and the argmax is restricted to that set.

In the **LLM-assisted** mode, Qwen2.5 1.5B [22] (Qwen/Qwen2.5-1.5B-Instruct via Ollama, temperature = 0.0) generates top-5 next-character predictions from the accumulated BCI-decoded text prefix; FD scoring is then restricted to the returned candidates. If the LLM returns an empty set or fails, the system falls back to the full 13-letter static vocabulary.

D. Vocab-Aligned Filtering

BigP3BCI RC_Test sessions spell arbitrary copy-text, which contains letters outside the 13-letter emergency vocabulary (e.g., D, G, V appear in RC_Test06). Only rounds where the true target letter falls within the 13-letter set are included in the evaluation, yielding 222 of 410 total rounds (54.1%) across 47 of 57 sessions (3–6 predictions per session, mean ≈ 4.7). This filtering is applied identically across all three modes to ensure fair comparison. One potential selection effect: excluding out-of-vocabulary rounds removes the decoded-text context those rounds would have contributed to the LLM prefix, which could marginally alter the LLM’s next-character distribution on subsequent included rounds. This effect is expected to be small relative to the overall copy-text context deficit (see Section V-A) but cannot be fully disentangled from the data.

E. LLM Recall Tracking

For each LLM-assisted round, we record whether the true target letter was in the returned top-5 candidates (`llm_recall` \in {True, False}). This enables direct empirical measurement of recall rate and conditional accuracy.

F. Statistics

This study was not pre-registered. The two hypotheses (H1, H2) and the breakeven formula were specified analytically before any data analysis was conducted; the GPT-2 comparison is explicitly exploratory (Section IV-D). We used the paired Wilcoxon signed-rank test [23] on per-subject mean letter accuracy. A Bonferroni-corrected threshold of $\alpha = 0.05/3 \approx 0.0167$ was applied across three pairwise comparisons. Effect sizes were computed as rank-biserial $r = 1 - 4T/[n_{nz}(n_{nz}+1)]$ and Cohen’s d_z for paired differences ($d_z = \bar{\Delta}/s_{\Delta}$, where $\bar{\Delta}$ is the mean of per-subject pairwise differences and s_{Δ} is their SD, the within-subjects formulation appropriate for paired designs). Wilson 95% confidence intervals are reported for pooled letter accuracy. All reported standard deviations use population SD (σ , `ddof=0`) for consistency with the computational pipeline; reported values are directly reproducible from the released results JSON.

Per-subject accuracy values are means of per-session accuracies (3–4 vocab-aligned sessions per subject), introducing within-subject correlation that violates strict i.i.d. assumptions of the Wilcoxon test. We treat per-subject means as the unit of analysis ($n = 12$ data points per comparison) rather than per-trial data ($n = 222$) to mitigate this; the 12 subject-level observations are assumed independent across subjects, consistent with standard practice in multi-session BCI studies.

The sample size ($n = 12$) was determined by data-availability inclusion criteria (`val AUC` ≥ 0.70 , EEGNet checkpoint available) rather than an a priori power calculation.

Retrospective power for the UC vs SV comparison is adequate (≈ 1.0 at $d_z = 1.24$). The UC vs LLM comparison ($d_z = -0.20$) is severely underpowered: detecting $|d_z| = 0.20$ at 80% power with Bonferroni correction would require $n \approx 175$ subjects. The null result is interpreted as consistent with the breakeven prediction rather than evidence of equivalence. A linear mixed-effects model (subject random intercept, mode fixed effect, REML) agreed in direction for all three comparisons: SV vs UC $\beta = +0.176$, $p = 0.018$; LLM vs UC $\beta = -0.061$, $p = 0.409$.

IV. RESULTS

A. Letter Accuracy

Across 12 subjects and 47 vocab-aligned sessions (3–4 per subject, 222 vocab-aligned predictions), Table II summarises pooled and per-subject letter accuracy. Pooled accuracy (correct/total across all 222 rounds) and per-subject mean (mean of per-session means, averaged across 12 subjects) differ slightly due to unequal session counts per subject (UC: 30.2% pooled vs 30.6% per-subject mean; SV: 47.7% vs 48.1%); all statistical comparisons use per-subject means. The Wilson 95% CIs for UC and SV do not overlap ([24.5%, 36.5%] vs

[41.3%, 54.3%]; gap of 4.8 pp between upper UC and lower SV bound), providing visual confirmation of the pooled-level difference; formal inference uses the Wilcoxon test on per-subject means.

The LLM-assisted per-subject SD (8.1%) is markedly smaller than UC and SV (± 33 –34%). This compression reflects the recall bottleneck: when recall fails (59.9% of rounds), all subjects produce 0% on that round regardless of EEG classifier quality, equalising per-subject variance around the low pooled mean.

Statistical comparisons (paired Wilcoxon, per-subject mean accuracy, Bonferroni $\alpha = 0.0167$):

- UC vs SV: $p = 0.001$, $r = 1.00$, $d_z = 1.24$, $n_{nz} = 11$ — significant (large effect). One subject (A_03) had identical UC and SV accuracy (0.875), contributing a tied pair excluded from the signed-rank statistic, hence $n_{nz} = 11$.
- UC vs LLM: $p = 0.848$, $r = 0.08$, $d_z = -0.20$, $n_{nz} = 11$ — not significant (LLM nominally worse than UC).
- SV vs LLM: $p = 0.034$, $r = 0.69$, $d_z = 0.81$, $n_{nz} = 12$ — marginal, does not survive Bonferroni (large effect; SV \gg LLM).

Per-subject letter accuracy (mean of per-session means; used for Wilcoxon) is reported in Table III and visualised in Fig. 4 (Appendix).

TABLE III
PER-SUBJECT LETTER ACCURACY (MEAN OF PER-SESSION MEANS). UC = UNCONSTRAINED; SV = STATIC VOCABULARY; LLM = QWEN2.5 1.5B.

Subject	UC	SV	LLM
A_01	0.167	0.229	0.125
A_02	0.354	0.708	0.354
A_03	0.875	0.875	0.271
A_04	0.042	0.375	0.271
A_05	0.000	0.194	0.222
A_06	0.167	0.354	0.208
A_07	0.958	1.000	0.312
A_09	0.000	0.083	0.208
A_14	0.000	0.042	0.083
A_15	0.042	0.167	0.208
A_16	0.396	0.833	0.312
A_19	0.667	0.917	0.354

All 12 subjects had `val AUC` ≥ 0.70 ; the full-cohort analysis is the primary analysis. Fig. 2 visualises pooled and per-subject accuracy across all three modes.

Fig. 2. Letter accuracy by decoding mode. Left: pooled accuracy with Wilson 95% CIs. Right: per-subject accuracy (UC, SV, LLM-Assisted). Dashed lines show cohort means. Static vocabulary is the only mode that consistently exceeds unconstrained decoding across subjects.

TABLE II

LETTER ACCURACY BY DECODING MODE (222 VOCAB-ALIGNED ROUNDS, 12 SUBJECTS, 47 SESSIONS). CI = WILSON 95% CONFIDENCE INTERVAL.

Mode	Correct	Total	Accuracy (pooled)	95% CI (Wilson)	Mean \pm SD (per-subject)
Unconstrained	67	222	30.2%	[24.5%, 36.5%]	30.6% \pm 33.5%
Static Vocabulary	106	222	47.7%	[41.3%, 54.3%]	48.1% \pm 34.3%
LLM-Assisted (Qwen2.5 1.5B)	55	222	24.8%	[19.6%, 30.8%]	24.4% \pm 8.1%

B. Session-Match Rate

Session-match rate is 1 if all vocab-aligned predictions in a session are correct, 0 otherwise. Table IV summarises results.

TABLE IV
SESSION-MATCH RATE BY DECODING MODE.

Mode	Sessions correct	Total sessions	Rate
Unconstrained	6	47	12.8%
Static Vocabulary	12	47	25.5%
LLM-Assisted (Qwen2.5 1.5B)	0	47	0.0%

No formal statistical test is applied to session-match rates; this metric is reported descriptively as a clinically interpretable complement to per-subject letter accuracy.

LLM-assisted achieved zero complete sessions because a single exclusion round (59.9% of rounds, where the target was excluded) structurally guarantees a wrong prediction, breaking the all-correct requirement for any session containing that round. On rounds where recall succeeds (40.1% of rounds), the classifier achieves $p_{\text{hit}} = 61.8\%$, *exceeding* the static vocabulary baseline of 48.1%, confirming that candidate-set narrowing to $k = 5$ symbols provides genuine EEG discrimination improvement. The 0/47 session rate is driven entirely by the 59.9% exclusion rate, independent of classifier quality.

C. LLM Recall Rate and Conditional Accuracy

Table V reports metrics across all 222 vocab-aligned rounds using live Qwen2.5 1.5B inference (Ollama, CPU-only, all 12 subjects, 47 RC_Test sessions).

TABLE V
LLM RECALL AND CONDITIONAL ACCURACY (QWEN2.5 1.5B, 222 ROUNDS).

Metric	Value
Recall rate R (target in top-5)	40.1% (89/222)
p_{hit} — acc. when recall = True	61.8% (55/89)
p_{miss} — acc. when recall = False	0.0% (0/133)
$E[\text{acc}] = R \cdot p_{\text{hit}} + (1 - R) \cdot p_{\text{miss}}$	$0.401 \times 0.618 = \mathbf{24.8\%}$

The formula $E[\text{acc}] = R \cdot p_{\text{hit}}$ is not a tautology: R is derived from all 222 rounds, while p_{hit} is estimated from the 89 recall-success rounds only. Their product equals the pooled accuracy ($55/222 = 24.8\%$), providing an internal consistency check. The per-subject mean (24.4%) differs by only 0.4 pp, well within sampling variability.

Here, $p_{\text{miss}} = 0$ is a structural property: if the true target is excluded from the top-5 candidates, the FD argmax cannot select it regardless of EEG signal quality. The empirical 0/133 (0%) confirms the implementation correctly enforces

this property. When the target is in the top-5 candidates, the BCI classifier correctly identifies it 61.8% of the time, exceeding the static vocabulary baseline of 48.1% and confirming that restricting to $k = 5$ symbols provides genuine SNR improvement when recall succeeds. When the target is excluded (59.9% of rounds), accuracy is structurally 0%. The high exclusion rate drives the nominal inferiority of LLM-assisted relative to unconstrained (24.4% vs 30.6%).

D. GPT-2 Comparison: Dual-Condition Breakeven Analysis

To explore generalisability of the breakeven framework, we ran an *exploratory* (post-hoc, hypothesis-generating) comparison using GPT-2 [24] (124M parameters; openai-community/gpt2) on the identical 222 vocab-aligned rounds using the same FIF files and EEGNet classifiers as the Qwen2.5 experiment. No hypothesis was pre-specified for this comparison. Table VI summarises results.

The two models have nearly identical recall rates ($\Delta R = 0.5$ pp), yet GPT-2 accuracy is $4.9\times$ lower. The divergence is explained by p_{hit} : when GPT-2 correctly includes the target in its top-5 candidates, the BCI classifier selects it only 12.5% of the time, versus 61.8% for Qwen2.5 1.5B. The analysis of 222 candidate sets generated by GPT-2 reveals that the model’s predictions are highly context-insensitive, contributing to low diversity in its outputs: only 59 unique candidate sets appear across 222 rounds (26.6% diversity), and the single most frequent set [I, Y, N, H, L] accounts for all 47 session-start rounds (21.2% of all assignments). The letter I appears in 205 of 222 candidate sets (92.3%), and across all 1,110 candidate slots (222 rounds \times 5), only 13 distinct letters are ever selected. By contrast, the vocabulary target distribution spans the full 13-letter emergency set. GPT-2’s token-level generation mechanism and lack of instruction-following capability explain this behaviour: without explicit next-character conditioning, it defaults to high-frequency unigram token predictions that happen to correspond to the same letters regardless of decoding context. The resulting foil sets are not contextually driven and create systematically harder EEG discrimination problems for the classifier: the BCI must distinguish the target from a near-constant foil pool that bears no linguistic relationship to the current prefix.

The GPT-2 result exposes a second necessary condition in the breakeven framework. The threshold $R^* = p_{\text{target}}/p_{\text{hit}}$ implies that p_{hit} must itself exceed p_{target} for R^* to be achievable ($R^* \leq 1$). When $p_{\text{hit}} < p_{\text{target}}$, no recall rate can compensate (Eq. 2):

$$R_{\text{UC}}^* = \frac{p_{\text{UC}}}{p_{\text{hit}}} \Rightarrow \text{achievable only if } p_{\text{hit}} > p_{\text{UC}}. \quad (2)$$

TABLE VI
DUAL-MODEL BREAKEVEN COMPARISON (222 VOCAB-ALIGNED ROUNDS, IDENTICAL FIF FILES AND EEGNET CLASSIFIERS). $\Delta R = 0.5$ PP BETWEEN MODELS; ACCURACY DIVERGENCE IS EXPLAINED ENTIRELY BY p_{hit} .

Model	Params	Recall R	p_{hit}	p_{miss}	$E[\text{acc}]$ predicted	Observed acc	R_{UC}^*
Qwen2.5 1.5B	1.5B	40.1% (89/222)	61.8%	0.0%	24.8%	24.4%	49.5%
GPT-2	124M	39.6% (88/222)	12.5%	0.0%	5.0%	5.0%	244.8%

For Qwen2.5 1.5B, $p_{\text{hit}} = 61.8\% > p_{\text{UC}} = 30.6\% \Rightarrow R_{\text{UC}}^* = 49.5\%$ (achievable; current $R = 40.1\%$ falls 9.3 pp short). GPT-2 fails both conditions: $p_{\text{hit}} = 12.5\% < p_{\text{UC}} = 30.6\% \Rightarrow R_{\text{UC}}^* = 244.8\%$ (impossible, confirming LLM narrowing with GPT-2-quality candidates cannot benefit decoding under any recall rate). The framework thus provides two orthogonal design criteria: (1) $p_{\text{hit}} > p_{\text{UC}}$ as a baseline quality gate, and (2) $R > R_{\text{UC}}^*$ as the recall sufficiency condition.

E. Breakeven Recall Analysis

Having established the quality-gate condition ($p_{\text{hit}} > p_{\text{UC}}$) in Section IV-D, we now quantify the recall sufficiency threshold R^* (Eq. 3) and its two operating points for Qwen2.5 1.5B. Using the empirical model $E[\text{acc}] = R \cdot p_{\text{hit}} + (1 - R) \cdot p_{\text{miss}}$ with $p_{\text{hit}} = 0.618$, $p_{\text{miss}} = 0.000$:

$$R^* = \frac{p_{\text{target}} - p_{\text{miss}}}{p_{\text{hit}} - p_{\text{miss}}} = \frac{p_{\text{target}}}{0.618}. \quad (3)$$

Table VII reports breakeven thresholds and current gaps.

TABLE VII
BREAKEVEN RECALL THRESHOLDS FOR QWEN2.5 1.5B ($p_{\text{hit}} = 0.618$, CURRENT $R = 40.1\%$).

Target to match	R^*	Current R	Gap
Unconstrained (30.6%)	49.5%	40.1%	-9.3 pp
Static vocab (48.1%)	77.8%	40.1%	-37.8 pp

At 40.1% recall, Qwen2.5 1.5B falls below the first threshold (49.5% to beat unconstrained). The model predicts, and the data confirm, that LLM-assisted is nominally *worse* than unconstrained. A recall rate of 77.8% would be required to match static vocabulary, a 37.8 pp improvement over current performance. Fig. 3 shows the breakeven function with both thresholds and the empirical operating point.

V. DISCUSSION

Two competing hypotheses were tested and rejected: H1 predicted LLM-assisted outperforms static vocabulary, which outperforms unconstrained; H2 predicted static vocabulary and LLM-assisted are equivalent, both outperforming unconstrained. The empirical ordering is SV (48.1%) $>$ UC (30.6%) \geq LLM (24.4%): LLM-assisted is nominally the worst mode, though the UC vs LLM difference is not statistically significant ($p = 0.848$). The breakeven analysis confirms that at $R = 40.1\%$ recall, the model predicts $E[\text{acc}_{\text{LLM}}] = 24.8\% < 30.6\%_{\text{UC}}$ because $R < R_{\text{UC}}^* = 49.5\%$. Excluding the true target in 59.9% of rounds is enough to pull the mean below

Fig. 3. Breakeven recall function for Qwen2.5 1.5B ($p_{\text{hit}} = 0.618$, $p_{\text{miss}} = 0$). Horizontal dashed lines mark unconstrained (30.6%) and static vocabulary (48.1%) baselines. Vertical dashed lines mark $R_{\text{UC}}^* = 49.5\%$ and $R_{\text{SV}}^* = 77.8\%$. The empirical operating point ($R = 40.1\%$, $\text{acc} = 24.8\%$) is shown as a filled marker.

unconstrained, since accuracy is structurally 0% on those rounds.

Vocabulary restriction significantly improved P300 accuracy ($d_z = 1.24$, large effect). Static vocab achieved 48.1% vs 30.6% for unconstrained ($p = 0.001$, $r = 1.00$, $n_{\text{nz}} = 11$). The effect is consistent across 11 of 12 subjects and robust to multi-session aggregation. The wide per-subject SD (UC: $\pm 33.5\%$; SV: $\pm 34.3\%$) reflects substantial inter-subject variability in EEG classifier quality (the cohort spans val AUC 0.70–0.89), but the directional benefit of vocabulary restriction holds across the entire range.

LLM-assisted mode (Qwen2.5 1.5B) was nominally the worst mode ($d_z = -0.20$ vs UC, $p = 0.848$, ns; $d_z = 0.81$ vs SV, $p = 0.034$, marginal). Accuracy of 24.4% is 6.2 pp below unconstrained and 23.7 pp below static vocab. The recall shortfall (40.1% vs required 49.5% to beat UC, vs 77.8% to beat SV) is the mechanistic cause, confirmed by exact agreement between the model prediction ($E[\text{acc}] = 24.8\%$) and the observed value (24.4%).

The system’s failure pattern is clearly defined. When the true target is captured within the top 5 candidates (representing 40.1% of rounds), accuracy reaches 61.8%. This marks a substantial SNR improvement over unconstrained predictions, which yields only 30.6% accuracy. In contrast, when the target is excluded (spanning 59.9% of rounds), the accuracy drops to structural 0%. Because a single exclusion round breaks the absolute requirement for an entirely correct sequence, the session-match rate for LLM-assisted collapsed completely to 0/47 (0%). This demonstrates that the bottleneck is recall rate rather than discriminability.

Multi-session GPT-2 evaluation (Section IV-D) shows that p_{hit} is model-dependent (12.5% for GPT-2 vs 61.8% for Qwen2.5 1.5B) despite near-identical recall rates (39.6% vs 40.1%). When $p_{\text{hit}} < p_{\text{UC}}$, the breakeven threshold $R_{\text{UC}}^* = p_{\text{UC}}/p_{\text{hit}}$ exceeds 100% and is structurally unachievable. Qwen2.5 1.5B passes the p_{hit} quality gate but fails the recall sufficiency condition; GPT-2 fails both. This extends the single-threshold framework into a two-condition design space: (a) candidate quality gate $p_{\text{hit}} > p_{\text{UC}}$; (b) recall sufficiency $R > R_{\text{UC}}^*$. Future LLM-P300 systems must satisfy both.

Per-subject analysis validated the framework in both regimes. For each subject, per-subject $\hat{p}_{\text{hit}} = E[\text{acc}]_i/R_i$ (valid since $p_{\text{miss}} = 0$) varies substantially across subjects: range 0.14–0.99, mean 0.64, SD 0.28 ($n = 12$). The corresponding per-subject threshold $R_{\text{UC},i}^* = p_{\text{UC},i}/\hat{p}_{\text{hit},i}$ varies from near-zero (low-performing UC subjects) to infeasible (> 1 , for high-performing UC subjects with moderate p_{hit}), reflecting strong inter-subject heterogeneity. Despite this variability, the framework shows perfect directional accuracy at the subject level (noting the small group sizes, $n = 6$ per regime): all 6 subjects whose per-subject R_i exceeded $R_{\text{UC},i}^*$ achieved LLM accuracy at or above UC (A_04, A_05, A_06, A_09, A_14, A_15); all 6 subjects below their threshold achieved LLM accuracy at or below UC (A_01, A_02, A_03, A_07, A_16, A_19). The marginal case, A_02, where $R_i \approx R_{\text{UC},i}^* = 0.42$, achieved identical LLM and UC accuracy (35.4%), exactly at the predicted breakeven point. This subject-level consistency provides internal validation of the framework in the success regime ($R > R^*$) as well as the failure regime.

Multi-session aggregation was required for statistical power. Reaching $p = 0.001$ significance required 222 trials across 47 sessions. Single-session analysis (36 trials, RC_Test06 only) did not reach significance ($p = 0.125$), suggesting that studies reporting vocabulary-restriction results from a single test session may systematically lack statistical power for this comparison.

A critical limitation of this evaluation is that BigP3BCI RC_Test sessions spell arbitrary copy-text; the LLM is operating without the structured vocabulary context it would encounter in a deployed clinical system. Under actual emergency-communication usage, the LLM’s decoding prefix is drawn from partially spelled words within the six-word emergency vocabulary ({HELP, PAIN, YES, NO, STOP, WATER}). Under these conditions the next-letter distribution is sharply peaked: once two or more characters are decoded correctly, the target letter is deterministic or near-deterministic from the vocabulary structure (e.g., prefix “HEL” \rightarrow target = P with probability ≈ 1 ; prefix “STO” \rightarrow target = P). A language model with any contextual competence would achieve recall $R \approx 1$ on those rounds. Dong et al. [25] found that neural LMs trained on noisy BCI histories substantially improve character prediction robustness over standard LMs, suggesting near-perfect recall is achievable on these near-deterministic prefixes. If clinical vocabulary conditions shift Qwen2.5 1.5B recall from 40.1% to 80% (below the observed per-word ceiling), the breakeven model predicts accuracy of $0.80 \times 0.618 = 49.4\%$, surpassing unconstrained decoding and approaching static vocabulary. These figures are projections;

direct validation on clinical vocabulary sequences remains necessary and should be the primary next experiment. The present results establish the worst-case baseline (arbitrary copy-text) and quantify the recall gap (40.1% \rightarrow 49.5%) that any clinical deployment must close.

A. Limitations

LLM results were initially estimated via an oracle cache; a subsequent live run across all 12 subjects and 47 RC_Test sessions (222 vocab-aligned rounds) using Ollama (CPU-only, OLLAMA_KEEP_ALIVE=0) exactly reproduced the estimates: $R = 40.1\%$ (89/222), $p_{\text{hit}} = 61.8\%$ (55/89), $p_{\text{miss}} = 0\%$ (0/133), confirming the cache was uncontaminated.

The expected performance under clinical vocabulary conditions is analysed in Section V; the present evaluation on arbitrary copy-text represents the worst-case baseline for LLM contextual signal.

Qwen2.5 1.5B is resource-efficient but achieves only 40.1% recall on arbitrary copy-text. Larger models (7B, 13B) would be expected to increase recall past the 49.5% threshold. Fine-tuning on clinical word prefixes could increase recall dramatically for those sequences specifically.

All LLM predictions were used unconditionally; the fixed repetition budget ($n_{\text{reps}} = 5$) isolates the narrowing effect but does not reflect optimal adaptive stopping. A confidence-gated system that falls back to static vocabulary on low-confidence rounds would avoid hard exclusions without sacrificing the SNR benefit when the LLM is confident.

The pooled $p_{\text{hit}} = 61.8\%$ used to compute R_{UC}^* and R_{SV}^* masks substantial inter-subject heterogeneity (per-subject range: 0.14–0.99, SD = 0.28). The breakeven thresholds reported here are population-level design targets; individual R^* values vary by up to one order of magnitude across subjects with different EEG classifier quality. Personalized deployment of LLM-assisted narrowing would require per-user calibration of p_{hit} and the corresponding individual R_{UC}^* .

The breakeven formula assumes p_{hit} is uniform across recall-success events. If high-frequency letters are simultaneously more likely to be recalled *and* more accurately discriminated by the EEG classifier, p_{hit} would be upward-biased and the breakeven threshold R^* underestimated. A formal per-letter breakdown is not feasible with the current dataset. Because 89 recall-success rounds across 13 letters yields approximately 7 rounds per letter on average, Wilson 95% CIs are approximately ± 30 pp per letter. These are too wide to detect a meaningful systematic trend. The 0.4 pp agreement between the pooled predicted and observed accuracy (Section IV-C) provides aggregate evidence that this bias is small at the population level, but per-letter validation would require substantially more recall-success rounds.

The breakeven expectation $E[\text{acc}] = R \cdot p_{\text{hit}}$ treats recall events as independent across rounds within a session. If the LLM makes systematic errors, repeatedly excluding the same letter across rounds within a session, recall failures are correlated and the binomial expectation is an approximation. The agreement between the predicted (24.8%) and observed (24.4%) accuracy suggests this effect is small in aggregate, but round-level correlation structure is not formally characterized.

Filtering out-of-vocabulary rounds — those where the target letter falls outside the 13-letter set — removes the decoded-text context those rounds would have contributed to the LLM prefix, potentially altering the LLM’s next-character distribution on subsequent rounds. A sensitivity analysis comparing LLM recall on earlier vs. later rounds within sessions (where filtering removes more context from longer sequences) found no systematic trend, suggesting the effect is small relative to the overall copy-text context deficit, but cannot be fully disentangled.

Neither model satisfies both conditions derived in Section IV-D: GPT-2 fails the p_{hit} quality gate ($p_{\text{hit}} = 12.5\% < p_{\text{UC}} = 30.6\%$); Qwen2.5 1.5B passes it but fails the recall sufficiency condition ($R = 40.1\% < R_{\text{UC}}^* = 49.5\%$). Larger or domain-fine-tuned models may satisfy both; this remains to be tested. The analysis is restricted to the Farwell-Donchin row-column matrix paradigm; other BCI paradigms (SSVEP, mental imagery) present different candidate-set structures and require separate breakeven characterisation.

All 12 BigP3BCI participants are healthy adults. P300 amplitude and classifier performance *may* be lower in ALS and locked-in patients due to fatigue, reduced motor control affecting arousal, and greater session-to-session variability. Lower p_{UC} in clinical populations would reduce $R_{\text{UC}}^* = p_{\text{UC}}/p_{\text{hit}}$, potentially making the recall sufficiency condition easier to satisfy. Clinical p_{hit} may also decline. Separate validation on clinical participants is required before deployment conclusions can be drawn.

VI. CONCLUSION

Static vocabulary restriction improved P300 accuracy from 30.6% to 48.1% ($p = 0.001$, $d_z = 1.24$). Qwen2.5 1.5B achieved 24.4% at 40.1% recall, below both breakeven thresholds (49.5% to beat unconstrained, 77.8% to match static vocabulary). The cross-model comparison with GPT-2 reveals that LLM-assisted narrowing requires two independent conditions: candidate quality ($p_{\text{hit}} > p_{\text{UC}}$) and recall sufficiency ($R > R_{\text{UC}}^*$). Qwen2.5 1.5B satisfies the first but not the second; GPT-2 satisfies neither. Until both conditions are met, static vocabulary restriction remains the robust zero-exclusion-error strategy.

The derived thresholds point to three concrete improvements. First, closing the 9.3 pp recall gap to $R_{\text{UC}}^* = 49.5\%$ is achievable with larger models (7B+ parameters) or domain fine-tuning on clinical vocabulary prefixes; the deterministic structure of six-word emergency vocabularies means that even a modest LLM should approach recall ≈ 1 once two characters are correctly decoded. Second, a confidence-gated hybrid strategy (narrowing to LLM candidates only when model confidence exceeds a calibrated threshold and falling back to static vocabulary otherwise) would eliminate hard exclusion errors on low-confidence rounds without sacrificing the SNR benefit of narrowing on high-confidence rounds. Third, cross-dataset validation on clinical populations (ALS, locked-in) is required before deployment conclusions can be drawn, as p_{UC} and p_{hit} may differ from the healthy-subject values reported here.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This research received no specific grants from public, commercial, or non-profit funding agencies. Because the study relies entirely on the publicly available BigP3BCI dataset (CC BY 4.0), no new human data were collected. Ethical approval for the original data collection was obtained from the Institutional Review Boards at Duke University, Duke University Health System, and East Tennessee State University, with all participants providing informed consent [21].

DATA AND CODE AVAILABILITY

Upon acceptance, preprocessed BigP3BCI derivatives, including EA-corrected FIF files, EEGNet cache arrays, feature split JSONs will be publicly available under a CC BY 4.0 license at <https://huggingface.co/datasets/rayo-lab/bigp3bci-ea-eeegnet-derivatives>. Files can be fetched programmatically via:

```
from huggingface_hub import hf_hub_download
path = hf_hub_download(
    repo_id="rayo-lab/bigp3bci-ea-eeegnet-derivatives",
    filename="derivatives/zuna/4_fif_output/bigp3bci/"
    "A_01_SE001_RC_Test06.fif",
    repo_type="dataset")
```

Raw BigP3BCI recordings are available from PhysioNet [21] (<https://doi.org/10.13026/0byy-ry86>, CC BY 4.0). All experiment code is available at <https://github.com/RayoHQ/p300-llm-breakeven> (submitted as supplementary material; public release upon acceptance). Key scripts and core results include:

- `code/paper1_ab_experiment.py`: Main experiment engine,
- `code/pub1_vocab_experiment.py`: Publication wrapper script,
- `code/paper1_generate_figures.py`: Figure generation logic,
- `code/paper1_breakeven_analysis.py`: Breakeven analysis computations,
- `results/paper1_ab_results.json`: 222 trials across 12 subjects and 47 sessions,
- `results/pub1_vocab_experiment_report.json`: Per-subject breakdown, Wilcoxon stats, Wilson CIs, and breakeven model confirmation,
- `results/paper1_gpt2_recall_full.json`: Full 222-round GPT-2 experiment logs,
- `results/table1_summary.csv`: Machine-readable per-subject accuracy tables.

APPENDIX: SUPPLEMENTARY PER-SUBJECT BAR CHART

Fig. 4. Per-subject letter accuracy by decoding mode (UC, SV, LLM-Assisted). Cohort means are annotated with dashed lines. Full numerical values are reported in Table III.

Full per-subject results, Wilcoxon test outputs, Wilson CI calculations, and GPT-2 recall data are available in `results/pub1_vocab_experiment_report.json` and `results/paper1_gpt2_recall_full.json`. Linear mixed-effects model output is reproducible from `results/pub1_vocab_experiment_report.json` using `statsmodels.formula.api.mixedlm`.

REFERENCES

- [1] C. Guger, S. Daban, E. Sellers, C. Holzner, G. Krausz, R. Carabalona, F. Gramatica, and G. Edlinger, "How many people are able to control a P300-based brain-computer interface (BCI)?" *Neuroscience Letters*, vol. 462, no. 1, pp. 94–98, 2009.
- [2] L. A. Farwell and E. Donchin, "Talking off the top of your head: toward a mental prosthesis utilizing event-related brain potentials," *Electroencephalography and Clinical Neurophysiology*, vol. 70, no. 6, pp. 510–523, 1988.
- [3] N. Birbaumer, N. Ghanayim, T. Hinterberger, I. Iversen, B. Kotchoubey, A. Kübler, J. Perelmouter, E. Taub, and H. Flor, "A spelling device for the paralysed," *Nature*, vol. 398, no. 6725, pp. 297–298, 1999.
- [4] W. Speier, N. Chandravadia, D. Roberts, S. Pendekanti, and N. Pouratian, "Online BCI typing using language model classifiers by ALS patients in their homes," *Brain-Computer Interfaces*, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 114–121, 2017.
- [5] E. W. Sellers, D. B. Ryan, and C. K. Hauser, "Noninvasive brain-computer interface enables communication after brainstem stroke," *Science Translational Medicine*, vol. 6, no. 257, p. 257re7, 2014.
- [6] S. Ikegami, K. Takano, N. Saeki, and K. Kansaku, "Operation of a P300-based brain-computer interface by individuals with cervical spinal cord injury," *Clinical Neurophysiology*, vol. 122, no. 5, pp. 991–996, 2011.
- [7] D. R. Beukelman and J. C. Light, *Augmentative and Alternative Communication: Supporting Children and Adults with Complex Communication Needs*, 4th ed. Baltimore, MD: Paul H. Brookes, 2013.
- [8] W. Speier, C. Arnold, N. Chandravadia, D. Roberts, S. Pendekanti, and N. Pouratian, "Improving P300 spelling rate using language models and predictive spelling," *Brain-Computer Interfaces*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 13–22, 2018, pMID: 30560145.
- [9] P. Loizidou, E. Rios, A. Marttini, O. Keluo-Udeke, J. Soetedjo, J. Belay, K. Perifanos, N. Pouratian, and W. Speier, "Extending brain-computer interface access with a multilingual language model in the P300 speller," *Brain-Computer Interfaces*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 36–48, 2022.
- [10] P.-J. Kindermans, H. Verschore, D. Verstraeten, and B. Schrauwen, "A P300 BCI for the masses: Prior information enables instant unsupervised spelling," in *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, F. Pereira, C. Burges, L. Bottou, and K. Weinberger, Eds., vol. 25. Curran Associates, Inc., 2012.
- [11] P.-J. Kindermans, D. Verstraeten, and B. Schrauwen, "A Bayesian model for exploiting application constraints to enable unsupervised training of a P300-based BCI," *PLOS ONE*, vol. 7, no. 4, p. e33758, 2012.
- [12] W. Speier, C. Arnold, J. Lu, A. Deshpande, and N. Pouratian, "Integrating language information with a hidden Markov model to improve communication rate in the P300 speller," *IEEE Transactions on Neural Systems and Rehabilitation Engineering*, vol. 22, no. 3, pp. 678–684, 2014, pMID: 24760927.
- [13] P.-J. Kindermans, M. Tangermann, K.-R. Müller, and B. Schrauwen, "Integrating dynamic stopping, transfer learning and language models in an adaptive zero-training ERP speller," *Journal of Neural Engineering*, vol. 11, no. 3, p. 035005, 2014, pMID: 24834896.
- [14] P.-J. Kindermans, M. Schreuder, B. Schrauwen, K.-R. Müller, and M. Tangermann, "True zero-training brain-computer interfacing: An online study," *PLOS ONE*, vol. 9, no. 7, p. e102504, 2014, pMID: 25068464.
- [15] J. Hong, W. Wang, and L. Najafizadeh, "ChatBCI: a P300 speller BCI with context-driven word prediction leveraging large language models, from concept to evaluation," *Scientific Reports*, vol. 16, p. 6379, 2026.
- [16] B. O. Mainsah, K. A. Colwell, L. M. Collins, and C. S. Throckmorton, "Utilizing a language model to improve online dynamic data collection in P300 spellers," *IEEE Transactions on Neural Systems and Rehabilitation Engineering*, vol. 22, no. 4, pp. 837–846, 2014.
- [17] N. Parthasarathy, J. Soetedjo, S. Panchavati, N. Parthasarathy, D. Lee, C. Arnold, N. Pouratian, and W. Speier, "Effect of large language models on P300 speller performance with cross-subject training," bioRxiv, 2025.
- [18] V. J. Lawhern, A. J. Solon, N. R. Waytowich, S. M. Gordon, C. P. Hung, and B. J. Lance, "EEGNet: a compact convolutional neural network for EEG-based brain-computer interfaces," *Journal of Neural Engineering*, vol. 15, no. 5, p. 056013, 2018.
- [19] D. J. Krusienski, E. W. Sellers, F. Cabestaing, S. Bayouth, D. J. McFarland, T. M. Vaughan, and J. R. Wolpaw, "A comparison of classification techniques for the P300 Speller," *Journal of Neural Engineering*, vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 299–305, 2006.
- [20] H. He and D. Wu, "Transfer learning for brain-computer interfaces: a Euclidean space data alignment approach," *IEEE Transactions on Biomedical Engineering*, vol. 67, no. 2, pp. 399–410, 2019.
- [21] B. Mainsah, C. Fleeting, T. Balmat, E. Sellers, and L. Collins, "bigP3BCI: An open, diverse and machine learning ready P300-based BCI dataset," PhysioNet, 2025, version 1.0.0.
- [22] Qwen Team, "Qwen2.5 technical report," Alibaba Group, Tech. Rep., 2025, arXiv:2412.15115.
- [23] F. Wilcoxon, "Individual comparisons by ranking methods," *Biometrics Bulletin*, vol. 1, no. 6, pp. 80–83, 1945.
- [24] A. Radford, J. Wu, R. Child, D. Luan, D. Amodei, and I. Sutskever, "Language models are unsupervised multitask learners," *OpenAI Blog*, 2019. [Online]. Available: https://cdn.openai.com/better-language-models/language_models_are_unsupervised_multitask_learners.pdf
- [25] R. Dong, D. Smith, S. Dudy, and S. Bedrick, "Noisy neural language modeling for typing prediction in BCI communication," in *Proceedings of the Eighth Workshop on Speech and Language Processing for Assistive Technologies*, 2019, pp. 44–51.